

Design and Implementation of a LoRa-Based Drone Audio Message Broadcasting System

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Abstract : This paper presents the design and implementation of a drone-based audio message broadcasting system using LoRa (Long Range) wireless communication technology. The system addresses a communication gap observed in several localities in Benin, where public announcements are still delivered by traditional town criers prone to human error. The proposed system consists of two electronic blocks: a ground-based transmitter unit and an airborne receiver unit mounted on a DJI Mini 2 drone. The transmitter block, built around an ESP32 microcontroller and a LoRa SX1278 Ra-02 module, receives broadcast commands from a web-based frontend via a Node.js server. The receiver block, also based on an ESP32 and LoRa module, retrieves pre-recorded audio files from a micro SD card and plays them through MAX98357A digital audio amplifiers connected to 8Ω loudspeakers. Circuit design was performed using KiCad EDA and the system was validated through functional testing. The total implementation cost was approximately 511,800 FCFA (roughly USD 853). Results confirm the feasibility of deploying UAV-based audio broadcasting systems for community communication in sub-Saharan Africa.

Keywords: Drone, UAV, LoRa, audio broadcasting, ESP32, IoT, embedded systems, Benin

1. INTRODUCTION

Rapid technological advancement has opened new possibilities for improving public communication systems, particularly in urban and peri-urban environments. In several localities across Benin, including Adjara, Porto-Novo, and Ouidah, community announcements of social, political, or public health interest are still conveyed by traditional messengers known as gongoneurs, who relay information using megaphones. The fidelity of such communication depends entirely on human reliability, which introduces risks of misinterpretation or message alteration.

The proliferation of low-cost Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) and embedded wireless communication modules now makes it technically feasible to automate this process. A drone-mounted audio system could broadcast pre-recorded messages with high fidelity across targeted geographic areas, eliminating human error and extending reach to areas that are difficult to access on foot.

This paper proposes a system that integrates a DJI Mini 2 consumer drone with a custom-built LoRa-based electronic payload capable of broadcasting audio messages on command from a remote web interface. The system is designed to be low-cost, modular, and operable by non-specialists.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews related work. Section 3 describes the system architecture. Section 4 details the hardware and software design. Section 5 presents implementation and PCB realization. Section 6 reports functional test results. Section 7 concludes and outlines future work.

2. RELATED WORK

UAVs have been extensively studied for communication-related applications. Researchers have explored their use as aerial base stations for extending wireless network coverage in disaster-stricken areas [1], and as relay nodes for IoT sensor data collection in agricultural settings [2].

LoRa technology, operating in the sub-GHz ISM band, has gained significant attention for its long-range, low-power characteristics well suited for IoT applications [3]. Its ability to transmit data over several kilometers with minimal power consumption positions it as an ideal communication layer for embedded drone payloads.

Audio broadcasting via drones has received comparatively less attention in academic literature. Commercial solutions for drone-mounted loudspeaker systems typically rely on proprietary radio links and real-time audio streaming. The present work differs by using LoRa-based command signaling combined with onboard SD card audio storage, reducing bandwidth requirements and improving reliability in low-connectivity environments. The use of ESP32 for I2S-based audio playback combined with LoRa has been demonstrated in internet radio projects [4], establishing technical feasibility of the core approach.

3. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The proposed system follows a client-server-hardware architecture composed of three layers: a React-based web frontend, a Node.js / Express.js backend with MongoDB database, and two custom ESP32-based electronic hardware blocks. Figure 1 presents the functional block diagram of the complete system, showing the transmitter (ground unit) and the receiver (airborne unit) and their interconnections.

Figure 1: Functional block diagram — Transmitter (top) and Receiver (bottom)

The frontend allows the operator to record or upload an audio message in MP3 format, select broadcast locations on a map, and trigger storage and playback commands. The server converts MP3 files to WAV format, generates a download link, and stores it with GPS coordinates in MongoDB. Two API endpoints are exposed: one for the airborne receiver to fetch the audio file, and one for the ground transmitter to poll for playback commands.

The Transmitter Block (ground unit) consists of an ESP32 and a LoRa SX1278 Ra-02 that polls the server for commands. Upon receipt, it encodes the project identifier and transmits it via LoRa at 433 MHz to the drone. The Receiver Block (airborne unit), also ESP32 + LoRa, connects to the server over Wi-Fi, downloads the audio file to a micro SD card, then upon receiving the LoRa command, streams the WAV file via I2S to two MAX98357A amplifiers driving 8Ω loudspeakers.

4. HARDWARE AND SOFTWARE DESIGN

4.1 Component Selection and Justification

The ESP32 DevKit V1 was selected for its dual-core processing, integrated Wi-Fi/Bluetooth, and SPI/I2C/I2S peripheral support. The LoRa SX1278 Ra-02 module operates at 433 MHz, a frequency band declared freely usable by ARCEP (Benin's telecommunications regulator) for independent IoT networks [5], ensuring full regulatory compliance.

The MAX98357A Class-D digital amplifier integrates DAC conversion via I2S and delivers 1.8W into 8Ω at 5V. Two units were used for stereo output. Speaker compatibility was verified: amplifier output power (1.8W) is below speaker rated power (3W), so no damage risk exists. Both blocks are powered by a 3.7V 2000mAh LiPo battery managed by a LiPo Rider Plus board providing regulated 5V output. Decoupling capacitors of 100nF were placed at each ESP32 supply input to filter high-frequency noise.

4.2 Wiring Diagrams

Wiring diagrams were produced using Fritzing (open-source) to facilitate assembly and understanding of the hardware interconnections. Figures 2 and 3 show the wiring layouts of the transmitter and receiver blocks respectively.

Figure 2: Wiring diagram — Transmitter block (ground unit)

Figure 3: Wiring diagram — Receiver block (airborne unit)

4.3 Software Stack

Layer	Technology
Frontend	React, Tailwind CSS
Backend	Node.js, Express.js
Database	MongoDB
Firmware	Arduino IDE (C/C++ for ESP32)
PCB Design	KiCad EDA
Drone Control	DJI Fly (mobile application)

Table 1: Software stack overview

4.4 Web Interface

The web interface provides the operator with full control over the broadcast pipeline. Figure 4 shows the dashboard (left panel) for project management and history, the audio recording interface with map-based location selection (top right), and the MongoDB database view for stored locations (bottom right).

Figure 4: Web interface — Dashboard, audio recording, map selection, and database view

5. PCB DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

5.1 PCB Layout

After schematic capture in KiCad, both designs were transferred to the KiCad PCB editor for component placement and routing. Design rules were configured before running the auto-router. 3D visualization confirmed component clearances prior to fabrication. Table 2 summarizes PCB dimensions.

Block	Length (mm)	Width (mm)
Transmitter (Ground Unit)	79.99	57.69
Receiver (Airborne Unit)	109.40	59.91

Table 2: PCB dimensions

5.2 Assembly and Financial Evaluation

Assembly followed a structured nine-step procedure per block: drilling of mounting holes, soldering of module headers, installation of ESP32, LoRa module and antenna connection via SMA connector, OLED display wiring, SD card reader integration (receiver only), MAX98357A amplifier integration via I2S (receiver only), and loudspeaker connection. The receiver payload was mechanically attached to the DJI Mini 2 frame without structural modification.

Table 3 presents the full project cost breakdown. The total cost of approximately USD 853 is dominated by the drone platform (USD 650); the custom electronic payload alone costs approximately USD 203.

Item	Unit (FCFA)	Qty	Total (FCFA)
ESP32 DevKit V1	6,200	2	12,400
LoRa SX1278 Ra-02	5,400	2	10,800
LoRa Antenna 5dBi 433MHz	6,000	2	12,000
OLED Display 0.96"	3,500	2	7,000
Locking Push Button	1,000	2	2,000
Loudspeaker 8Ω 3W	3,000	2	6,000
LiPo Battery 3.7V 2000mAh	12,000	2	24,000
LiPo Rider Plus	5,000	2	10,000
LiPo Capacity Indicator	2,000	2	4,000
Micro SD Reader	2,300	1	2,300
SD Card	1,000	1	1,000
DJI Mini 2 Drone	390,000	1	390,000
Terminal Block 2-pin	100	2	200
Capacitor 100nF	100	2	200
Labour	3,000	1	6,000
PCB Fabrication	—	—	7,300
Wiring	—	—	1,600
Contingency	—	—	15,000
TOTAL			511,800

Table 3: Project cost breakdown (approx. USD 853 at 600 FCFA/USD)

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

6.1 Functional Testing

Initial functional tests confirmed end-to-end system operation. The web interface successfully recorded and uploaded audio messages. The server correctly converted MP3 files to WAV, generated download links, and stored GPS coordinates in MongoDB. The receiver ESP32 downloaded and stored audio files on the SD card without data loss.

LoRa communication between the ground transmitter and the airborne receiver was validated, with data packets displayed in real time on both OLED screens, confirming successful transmission and reception. Upon receiving a playback command, the receiver correctly identified and read the audio file from the SD card, streamed it to the MAX98357A amplifiers, and produced clear audio output through both loudspeakers.

6.2 Discussion

The use of LoRa at 433 MHz proved appropriate, offering reliable data transmission within Benin's regulatory framework. Storing audio locally on the SD card rather than streaming over the air was a key architectural decision that reduced bandwidth requirements and made the system resilient to intermittent connectivity.

The total system cost is dominated by the drone platform. The electronic payload at approximately USD 203 is accessible for institutional deployment, particularly if lower-cost UAV platforms are considered in future iterations. Limitations include flight autonomy constrained by the DJI Mini 2 standard battery (~31 minutes) and the requirement for Wi-Fi connectivity to pre-load audio files before flight.

7. CONCLUSION

This paper presented the design, implementation, and testing of a LoRa-based drone audio message broadcasting system for community communication in Benin. The system integrates a React web frontend, a Node.js/MongoDB backend, and two custom ESP32-based boards communicating via LoRa at 433 MHz. Audio playback is achieved through MAX98357A amplifiers driving 8Ω loudspeakers mounted on a DJI Mini 2 drone.

The system demonstrates that low-cost off-the-shelf components can produce a functional UAV-based public address system with potential applications in community announcements, emergency communications, and smart city infrastructure in sub-Saharan Africa. Future enhancements include real-time audio broadcasting without prior SD card storage, autonomous GPS-guided flight along broadcast routes, and solar-powered ground station units for remote deployment.

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